

Pest resistance—insects

Influence of rice plant morphology on leaffolder incidence

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Rice crops in Bangladesh are attacked by three rice leaffolder species: *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley, and *M. exigua* (Butler) (Pyralidae: Lepidoptera). Larvae fold rice leaves lengthwise and feed on the green tissue, sometimes causing severe damage to the plant. We evaluated whether plant morphological characters influence leaffolder incidence.

Sixteen rice varieties and breeding lines were tested in the 1993 aus (summer) season under irrigated condition at the BRRI experimental farm in Gazipur. The experiment used a randomized complete block design with eight replications. Four-week-old seedlings of each entry were transplanted in 1-m² plot at 20-cm² hill spacing. Standard fertilizer and water management and other cultural operations were used. From booting to dough stages, three hills from each plot were selected at random for data collection. Border hills were not used. Plant height, number of total and folded leaves, and length and width of three flag leaves were determined.

Rice plant morphological characters and incidence of folded leaves caused by leaffolders. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1993 aus.*

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Green leaves hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Leaf blade (cm)		Folded leaves	
			Length	Width	(no. hill ⁻¹)	(%)
TKM6	147	42	56.1	1.04	0.38	0.9
IR32419-81-2-3-3	90	18	34.4	1.33	0.46	2.9
BR42419-44-2-3-2	97	19	32.4	1.28	0.58	3.0
S818B-10-2	91	32	32.2	1.34	0.63	2.2
BR4909-R1-R2	107	20	36.1	1.53	0.71	3.9
BR21	103	11	30.2	1.33	0.75	7.4
IR7156-J20-3-2-1-1	104	26	33.6	1.50	0.92	4.2
IR35366-40-3-3-2-2	93	25	32.6	1.32	0.96	3.9
IR31805-20-1-3-3	96	21	32.7	1.28	1.00	5.7
BR20	112	22	37.2	1.52	1.00	4.8
RP1442-2-2-3-5-1	87	18	30.5	1.31	1.21	6.9
BR1	82	19	33.1	1.25	1.25	7.1
IR42015-83-3-2-2	78	22	31.3	1.29	1.29	6.4
BR4490-B-69	108	28	36.9	1.54	1.46	5.1
B532B-PN-1-MS-1-KP-1	90	31	29.0	1.39	1.54	6.0
Purbachi	98	15	28.6	1.67	1.88	14.1
Mean	99	23	34.2	1.37	1.01	5.3
P < (ANOVA)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
cv%	3.9	-	9.7	10.2	-	-

*Data are av of 8 replications.

Test entries differed in plant height, number of green leaves hill⁻¹, and leaf blade length and width (see table). On average, leaffolders had folded 5.3% (0.9-14.1%) of the leaves. The entries also differed in rate of the incidence of folded leaves. Leaffolder-resistant variety TKM6, with narrow and long leaves, had the lowest level of folded leaves (0.9%), while Purbachi, with wide and short leaves, had the highest level (14.1%). There was no correlation between

folded leaves and plant height ($r = -0.336$) or green leaf number ($r = -0.0195$). However, the incidence of folded leaves was negatively correlated with leaf blade length ($r = -0.507$, $P < 0.05$) and positively correlated with leaf blade width ($r = 0.551$, $P < 0.05$). Results indicated that narrow and long leaves may offer some resistance against leaffolders compared with wide and short leaves in rice plants. ■

A virulent rice gall midge biotype in Manipur

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Five biotypes of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason have been identified in India. The GM population of Manipur was earlier described as biotype 3 of India, which conformed to the Ranchi GM biotype. However, a new pattern of reaction to differential rice varieties has been observed since 1991.

We evaluated a standard set of 10 differentials in four groups against the GM population of Iroisemba, Manipur, India

during the 1991-94 wet seasons. Thirty-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted in 3-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing.

Local recommended agronomic practices were followed. Gall midge incidence was recorded at 50 d after transplanting.

Reaction of differential rice varieties to gall midge (GM). Iroisemba, Manipur, India. 1991-94.

Group	Differential	GM incidence (%)									
		1991		1992		1993		1994		Mean	
		Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers	Hills	Tillers
I	W1263	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ARC6605	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
II	Phalguna	70	14.5	80	19.0	80	28.7	50	22.0	70	21.1
	ARC5984	60	11.9	35	11.7	95	21.0	70	18.0	65	15.7
III	CR-MR1523	65	13.5	50	15.2	60	22.0	35	10.6	52.5	15.3
	Velluthacheera	25	7.5	20	8.2	65	14.2	10	2.9	30	8.2
	Aganni	45	8.2	35	14.8	60	25.9	15	2.9	38.8	13.0
	Ptb10	30	8.1	40	10.2	85	16.1	35	6.5	47.5	10.2
IV	T1477	45	10.8	30	10.9	60	17.0	55	12.7	47.5	12.9
	TN1	80	22.7	65	17.5	95	27.0	60	15.8	75	20.8

Only W1263 and ARC6605 of group I showed resistant (R) reaction. Differentials of the other three groups showed a consistent susceptible (S) reaction (see table), thus depicting a new R-S-S-S type

response, which had not been previously reported in India. In supplementary studies, the Iroisemba population did not mate with any of the biotypes. We therefore propose

that this be considered a distinct biotype, 3M, that is different from the biotype 3 prevalent in Bihar (Ranchi) and Andhra Pradesh (Jagtiyal). ■

Pest resistance—other pests

Selection for weed competitiveness in upland rice

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Weed infestation is a major problem in upland and hydromorphic rice ecosystems in West Africa. Weeding is generally by hand, but in many cases effective weed control is impossible due to a shortage of labor. One way to reduce weed control inputs (hand weeding or herbicides) is to use weed-competitive cultivars to suppress and/or tolerate weeds. We conducted two experiments in 1994 to identify such cultivars.

In the first experiment, 16 promising cultivars selected in 1993 for their ability to suppress or tolerate weeds were evaluated under high-, medium-, and low-input management at M'be in Côte d'Ivoire. The experiment was laid out using a split-plot design with three replications and management levels as the main plot and varieties as the subplot.

Two *Oryza glaberrima* varieties, CG14 and CG20, gave the most tillers and leaf area under all levels of management. They had rapid vegetative growth and their plots had low weed biomass at 18 and 40 d after sowing (DAS) (see figure). Tall *O. sativa* varieties with high tillering ability such as WAB96-1-1 and SP4, suppressed weed growth. A third group, WAB181-18, WAB56-50, and WAB56-125, with high tillering ability, large leaf area, and intermediate stature (90-100 cm), tolerated weeds during the ripening stage. These cultivars had superior yields and were selected for detailed studies on weed competitiveness in 1995.

In a second experiment, 12 *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima* lines, previously selected to form a range of distinctly different plant types for plant height, tillering capacity, and

Relationship between tiller number and weed dry weight (wdw) under low (a, b) and medium (c) inputs.

^a1 = CG20, 2 = CGN, 3 = WAB56-50, 4 = WAB181-18, 5 = WAB56-104, 6 = WAB56-125, 7 = WAB96-1-1, 8 = IRAT144, 9 = WABC165, 10 = SP4, 11 = WAB99-1-1, 12 = IDSA10, 13 = ITAS257, 14 = IAC164, 15 = IRAT112, and 16 = CNA4136.

leaf type, were grown under two levels of weed control. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications and a plot size of 4 × 2.6 m.

Weed biomass at rice maturity differed among the varieties. There were interactions ($P < 0.003$) between weeding regime and cultivar for grain yield. Regression analysis across varieties and replicates showed that